

The Effect of Motivation, Competency and Compensation toward Performance

Fahmi Abdullah¹, Abdul Manan², Tanto Gatot Sumarsono³, Syarif Hidayatullah⁴

¹Post Graduate, University of Merdeka Malang, Malang, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer, University of Merdeka Malang, Malang, Indonesia

⁴Lecturer of Faculty Economy and Business, University of Merdeka Malang, Indonesia

Email address: ⁴syarif_ok@yahoo.com

Abstract— The aim of this study to identify and explain significant influence motivation Competence and compensation on the performance teacher. This research is an explanatory research with quantitative approach sample of 73 respondents. Data were collected by distributing questionnaires in vocational Yadika Bangil. Analysis of the data used is descriptive analysis and multiple linear analysis. The results showed that the variable compensation positive and significant impact on teacher performance (coefficient) of 67.9% and the remaining 32.1% is influenced by other variables.

Keywords— Motivation, competency, compensation and performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

An organization or institution that both the educational institution in which there is a system of teaching and human resources are good also. For an educational institution can run well if it has a competent faculty and high caliber for optimally manage educational institutions so that education energy performance can be improved. With advances in technology that is increasingly rapidly, cannot be used as reference is that an educational institution can develop. Because with good technology but human resources that do not support then certainly an educational institution cannot thrive. In addition, human resource planners will be the realization of a good educational institutions. In the management of labor competencies include some aspect that is competency-based input, competence transformational, and competency output. Besides human resources strategy also involves matter competence in technical ability, conceptual and human relations. The effect of competence in performance can be seen from the level of competence that have practical implications in human resource planning, it is envisaged that the competence of the knowledge and skills tend to be more real and relative emerged as one of the characteristics that employee owned.

Competent teachers also become one of the important factors for the growth of an educational institution, but not enough with a competent teacher not: less important a leader must also be able to provide motivation and compensation to be more active in its work but it is also the task in order to advance an educational institution, because basically the progress and development of an educational institution also depends on human resources management in it. In the learning process of course there are failures as well as successes. The role of a teacher is considered in this case, the success of teachers in fostering and improving the organization cannot be

separated from the motivation given by the leadership of the shelter. In a failure likewise not entirely caused by the failure of a private teacher can be a factor the lack of motivation of a leader of the shelter. Basically motivation is a crucial factor in the success of coaching is done by a teacher in terms of development and progress of an educational institution. A teacher will also be more motivated if the results of such work to get satisfactory compensation from the organization as a token of appreciation for his work them. In this case houses an educational institution makes a teacher becomes an important factor for the growth of the organization.

SMK Yadika Bangil is a private educational institution providing education as a form of participation in the framework of the Indonesian life. SMK Yadika that is located on Jl. Bader No. 09 Kalirejo Bangil Pasuruan has a total of 73 teachers and 23 employees and a janitor. Education Foundation Swakarya engaged in education which also administered vocational Yadika Bangil is still carrying out the vision and mission of the founders, in which prioritizes service and care for the children who are less fortunate, weak economies and alleviate children who do not have parents or orphan . Thus the purpose of the institution is not alone - the eye to seek profit but the first major and is providing services to children who need it. In order to maintain the consistency of teacher performance foundation that houses vocational education herself Yadika Bangil always conduct an evaluation of each end of the school year and will start the new school year. This is done with the hope it can be maintained consistent good performance conducted by a teacher. In this case the facts obtained in the last few years process undertaken by the foundation of self- employment education to teachers in vocational Yadika Bangil in getting poor results or in other words the performance of teachers in vocational Yadika Bangil tend to decrease. This is evidenced by the lack of some items that are used as a measuring tool in the evaluation of teacher performance. Evidenced by the above data that looks always increases that in the last 3 years value - average low performance of teachers, for example in 2015 amounted to 62.8%, meaning that the value of the level of the teacher's performance is only 37.2%.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

An information about an organization's performance is a very important thing is used for performance evaluation

process if the process is done for this organization are in line with the expected goals or not. But in reality there are still many companies that do not know or do not care about the performance of their employees in their own organization and their employer. Performance or a function of both individual and group work in an organization that is affected by a variety of factors to achieve organizational goals within a specified time (Tika, 2006: 71). Performance or work performance is a result of the work accomplished individual in performing tasks assigned to them based on skills, experience and sincerity as well as time. (Hasibuan, 2003: 94)

Performance is generally an employee reflected image of a group, but in the application correctly is not easy, due to human nature that consists of a wide variety of characters and feelings, as well as the character and abilities (Ruky 2006: 213). Based on the understanding of the performance of several expert opinions above can be concluded that the performance is a result of individual work achieved in applying the tasks assigned to them and how to contribute to the organization of a worker. In addition, the performance can also be called as a result achieved by the individual person, both in quality and quantity within an organization in accordance with the responsibilities given.

Motivation

To achieve something that aspired - aiming, as people must have motivation in the liver as a form or desire that can be used as a reference in personal development but it also became one of the tools that must be possessed by an organization. Motivation is a model for a power that manifested from himself an employee and it also will direct the behavior of these employees (Ivancevich and Donnelly, 2004: 98). Besides motivation can also mean a boost to grow or emerge from an individual that can give strength and guide the behavior in the work environment in the execution of their duties. Of motivation can be used as a reference in achieving the objectives but it is also supposed to be a personal human motivation are better than others.

A willingness to make efforts to achieve the goals of the organization which is dominated by an ability to satisfy a number of these individuals can also be interpreted from a motivation. Motivation as a driver so that an individual to be able passionate in work other than that workers can work together, work effectively and capable integrated to achieve a desired level of satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2007: 35).

Based on some insight may disirripulkan if the motivation to work is an activity that maintain, distribute and the resulting behavior of an individual to act with utmost to achieve what he has as a goal of an organization. The purpose of a company or organization with motivation was to ensure that the human resources within the company or individual can work according to what is desired by the company oganisasi or proficiency level.

Competency

Competency concept was widely discussed and is becoming a very popular trend. Among multinational companies that have reached up to a national company that

has developed, the term and concept of competency has been introduced by an author field of management of the United States in The Competence Manager. In the book Boyatzis said that business managers in the United States shall have the competence of business and economics expert if the United States does not want to be defeated Japan and Europe. (Ruky, 2006: 103)

Compensation

Compensation is very important for an individual to be an employee because of the magnitude of a compensation may reflect the size of an employee's performance among other employees. Besides compensation is often referred to as a tribute and interpreted as a form of awards given to employees for contribution or as a reward for what the workers gave to the organization (Panggabean, 2002: 87). Compensation is a broad understanding relating to its financial benefits by an individual through the employment relationship with the organization.

Any kind of compensation is a proof of the implementation of human resource management functions relating to all types of granting an individual awards as a form of reciprocity in implementing the tasks in the organization. Compensation of general purpose for identification interests and employees (Hasibuan, 2002: 35). Compensation may be calculated on the basis of job evaluation, calculation is based on the evaluation of a job to get decent compensation approach (worth) and fairness (equity). Compensation also is everything received by the worker instead of a worker's contribution to the company. (Rifai, 2010: 74)

So it can be concluded that the compensation is everything received by the worker either money, goods or the like as a reply of an outcome of a job at the company or organization. With the importance of an individual in the organization's work as well as companies need to provide a more attention to the worker so that more can be maximized in the task at companies and organizations, because of the compensation were deemed worthy motivation of a worker.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design Concepts

This study includes quantitative research, collecting data used in this research is to use the questionnaire to be filled out by respondents, in collecting data.

The sampling technique in this study do not exist or do not use sampling techniques in because of the small population so that all the population sampled, namely by 73 teachers. For fewer than 100 people, the number of samples taken as a whole. But if the population of more than 100 people, it can take 10-15% of the total population. The study design used was explanatory research method that is both explanation and aims to test a theory or hypothesis in order to strengthen or even reject the theory or hypothesis of existing research results. In this case the researchers tested on the influence of motivation, competence and compensation on teacher performance.

Through this explanatory study will be known how the correlation between two or more variables in both pattern,

direction, nature, shape and strength of the relationship.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

A validity test is used to determine the feasibility of items in a list (construct) a question of defining a variable, the list of these questions generally support a particular variable groups. (Bhuono, 2012: 67) test criteria used are comparing the test results with the numbers table on the basis of decision-making:

1. The results of the questionnaire items declared invalid if the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$
2. The results of the questionnaire items declared invalid if the value of $r_{arithmetic} < r_{table}$.

R table value is the value obtained from table r Product - Moment (two-tailed test). R value table can be obtained through df (degree of freedom). To obtain df (degree of freedom) can be done by:

$$Df = n - k$$

With the caption:

n is the number of respondents and k is the number of the questions in one variable.

As for the count r is the value of Corrected Item - Total Correlation which are later mucnul table after we do the test on the test results table in SPSS software.

Test Reliability

Actual reliability test is a tool to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of variables. A variable is said to be reliable or reliable if someone answers the fact is consistent or stable over time.

Based on respondents' answers score recapitulation data presented in the above table are analyzed with Cronbach alpha approach which is calculated by the program IBM SPSS Statistics 23 for Windows. With the results obtained at least reach 0.60.

Classic Assumption Test

Test multicoloniarity

A regression model free of multicoloniarity if VIF (Variance Inflation Factory) on each - each independent variable is not more than 10 (VIF <10) or the tolerance value of not less than 0.1 (tolerance > 0.1).

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.483	.236		1.961	.054		
	X1	-.027	.077	-.031	-.351	.727	.563	1.775
	X2	-.113	.066	-.143	1.730	.088	.651	1.537
	X3	.782	.104	.760	7.543	.000	.440	2.273

From the table above it is known that the calculation of VIF X1 = 1.775, X2 = 1.537, X3 = 2.273 these three variables have VIF <10, it can be stated that these three variables multicoloniarity pass the test.

Heterokedastisitas Test

Heterokedastisitas means the residual variation that is not the same for all observations or the presence of residual

variation which increases in the number of observations increases. Testing heterokedastisitas symptoms using the scatterplot.

From the picture above shows the point - the point spread at random, do not form a particular pattern is clear, and spread both above and below the number 0 on the y axis. This means that not happen heteroskedisitas in regression models.

Normality Test

To detect the normality of the data can be done by looking at the spread of the data (point - the point on the diagonal axis of the graph, ie if the data spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line, then this indicates that the data has been normally distributed.

From the picture above indicates that the data (point) spread around and approached the diagonal line. This indicates that the data of researchers that includes variables of motivation, competency and compensation normal distribution.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,483	,238		1,961	,054		
	X1	-,027	,077	-,031	-,351	,727	,563	1,775
	X2	,113	,066	,143	1,730	,088	,651	1,537
	X3	,782	,104	,760	7,543	,000	,440	2,273

From the coefficient table above we can analyze multiple linear analysis of unstandardized Coefficient column. So it can be in the know in the linear regression equation can research on the interpretation of multiple linear regression equation is as follows:

If the variable X1 (motivation). X2 (Competence), X3 (compensation) is considered no (zero) then the value of Y (teacher performance) at 463.

If there are additional variable values X1 (motivation), then the value of Y (Performance of teachers) will decline

If there is a value addition X2 (competence), here will be an increase.

If there is a value addition X3 (compensation), there will be an increase.

Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination (R²) aims to find out how big the influence of variable X to Y. In SPSS output coefficient of determination lies in the model summary, the value of R Square has a value of 0 to 1, the value of R square is said to be good if it has a value above 0.5. But for the multiple linear regression should then use the Adjusted R Square.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,832 ^a	,692	,679	,2222

In the summary table above models can be seen the value of Adjusted R square of 0.679. This means that teacher performance is influenced by motivation, competency and compensation amounting to 67.9%, while the remaining 32.1% is influenced by other factors such as learning support equipment, office stationery complete

Hypothesis Testing

Test model

Model F test aims to determine the influence of variable X ome simultaneously (together) to variable Y. simultaneous F test results can be seen from SPSS output of the ANOVA table simultaneous hypothesis testing can be seen by looking at the value (sig.), That means:

1. If the value (sig.) Is less than 0.05 (sig. <.05) then the hypothesis will be accepted.
2. If the value (sig.) Is greater than 0.05 (sig.> 0.05) then the hypothesis will be rejected.

In the table above there is a column ANOVA sig. with a value of 0.00 (sig. = 0.00) scores fall below 0.05 (0.00 <0.05)

means that this research hypothesis acceptable. The hypothesis of this study is that there is a simultaneous effect of motivation variables (X1), competence (X2) and compensation (X3) against teacher performance (Y).

Partial test (t test)

Testing this hypothesis aims to determine whether the four hypothesis supported by empirical data to see the results of calculations by SPSS to view the table coefficients In the table we can test the hypothesis by looking at the columns of t or with the level of significance. The hypothesis could be accepted if: t> t table or if sig. <0.05 hypothesis is rejected if: t <t table or if sig. > 0.05. t table calculated from two-tailed alpha = 5%, df - k. Where: k is the number of variables independent and df is a sample

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,483	,238		1,961	,054		
	X1	-,027	,077	-,031	-,351	,727	,563	1,775
	X2	,113	,066	,143	1,730	,088	,651	1,537
	X3	,782	,104	,760	7,543	,000	,440	2,273

Coefficients table analysis can be used to determine how much influence each of variable X to variable Y. From the table above coefficients can be known significant value for the variable XI (motivation) = 0.727 (sig. = 0.727)> 0.05. And the value of t = -0.351. While t table df = n - k = 73-3 =

70. t table = 1.994. Thus -0.351 t <t table 1.994. so we can conclude motivation variable does not affect the performance of teachers.

For significant value X2 (competence) = 0.088 (sig. = 0.088)> 0.05. And the value of t = 1.730. While t table = df - k = 73-3 = 70. t table = 1.994 and t = 1.730. So the 1,730 t <t table 1.994. So it can be concluded competence variable does not affect the performance.

While significant value X3 (compensation) = 0,000 (sig. = 0,000)> 0.05. And the value of t = 7.543. While t table = df - k = 73-3 = 70. t table = 1.994 and t = 7.543. So t count 7.543> t table 1.994. So it can be concluded compensation variables significantly influence performance.

This means that third hypothesis can be accepted. So we can conclude the variable compensation positive and significant impact on the performance of teacher. From coefficients table can be seen that the value of the variable B Coefficients unstandardized compensation (X3) equal to 0,782 bigger than the other variables, it can be concluded that the compensation (X3) is the most dominant variable on teacher performance.

Discussion of Results

Analysis of motivation variable descriptions, competency, compensation and Performance

Motivation in the form of the life-sustaining needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization needs. The main thing is the motivation to support the establishment of a team to carry out and complete the task difficult institution. As motivation as a driver in order to be able passionate people in work than that workers can work

together, work effectively and capable integrated to achieve a desired level of satisfaction

Competence in shape by personal character, self-concept, knowledge, skills and motivation. The main thing that supports competency is able to provide guidance and assistance to other colleagues. Competence as a characteristic of individuals who could be shown, that contains about knowledge, skills and behaviors that can result in performance and work performance.

Compensation in the form of the basic pay, performance-based wages, indirect wages, as well as the achievements and awards. The main thing that supports the compensation is given the opportunity to enhance your career. Namely compensation payments of any kind either reward or gift that is given to workers who later appeared arising from such work motivation.

Performance in shape by working achievement, responsibility, obedience, honesty, cooperation, and initiative. The main thing that supports the performance is to give ideas for improvements agencies. The performance level of achievement is a result in order to realize the objectives of a company.

The influence of the motivation, competence and compensation on Performance

Motivation in this study had no effect and has a slope or a negative direction on teacher performance, this indicates that the motivation of teachers does not affect performance, otherwise more in teacher motivation is then reduced performance. The observations were done by researchers motivational factors that make has an impact and has a negative direction this is caused factors of age and seniority teachers. Each task made as an opportunity to improve career should be able to increase motivation but in this case did not happen to the teacher even though the institution to reward teachers with higher loyalty and work ethic. The results of this study are inconsistent with Adreani (2017) which states that motivation positive effect on performance.

Competence in this study had no effect on the performance of teachers. This is evidenced by the many teachers who do not agree with the beliefs of the duties for the good of the institution but it is also the teacher does not put himself as part of an existing work but it is also the number of teachers who did not know about the technical work related to the scope of work. The results of this study are not consistent with a study done Ismail (2016) which states bahwasannya competence affect the performance.

Compensation significantly affect the performance of teachers and a variable the dominant influence on the performance of teachers. This shows that salaries adjusted to the standard specified but it is also the salary given by the length of service and also given the opportunity to advance your career. Compensation becomes a trigger for a teacher in

order to get a reward for the work that is done. This study is in line with a study done Pratama (2015) which states compensation effect on performance.

V. CONCLUSION

- A. Motivation was formed by life-sustaining needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs. The main thing supported the motivation was made a group and complete a difficult task from the institution. The compensation was formed by personal character, self-concept, knowledge, skills, and motivation. It can support the motivation was gave the lesson or help the other worker partner. It was formed basic salary, salary based on the performance, indirect salary, and reward. The main thing that supports compensation is it gives the opportunity to increase their career. The performance was created by the work achievement, responsibility, honesty, obedience, cooperation, and initiatives. Besides supporting performance is to provide ideas for improvement of the institution.
- B. The compensation and competence were an effect on the performance of teachers SMK Yadika Bangil. However, it did not happen on motivation, motivation does not affect the performance of the teacher in SMK Yadika Bangil. It happened because of a lot of teachers who belonged to a senior who has been very long in terms of providing a learning. Next, this condition can lead to the emergence of a sense of bore, they do not have passion in teaching and other duties. However, it was different from the teacher who has the competency and supported the existence of appropriate compensation expectations, then this sort of thing can affect the performance of the teacher.
- C. The dominant was an effect of compensation on a performance of teachers SMK Yadika Bangil. It shows that the main things that ought to be considered to improve the performance of the teachers SMK Yadika Bangil are increased the compensation.

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